

Comparative Evaluation of the Clinical Accuracy of E-Pex and Propex Pixi Electronic Apex Locators for Working Length Determination in the Presence of Different Root Canal Irrigants: An in Vivo Study

Zalak Jain¹
Amit Eppar²
Sonal Bansal³
Malwika Sisodiya⁴
Deepshikha Mishra⁵
Aarya Agarwal⁶

PG Student¹
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research
Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student²
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research
Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Professor³
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research
Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

Professor⁴
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research
Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student⁵
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research
Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

PG Student⁶
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research
Centre
Gwalior, M.P., India

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Abstract

Background

Accurate working length determination is essential for successful endodontic treatment, as it directly influences cleaning, shaping, and obturation of the root canal system. Electronic apex locators (EALs) have become an important adjunct in endodontic practice because of their improved accuracy and reduced dependence on radiographs. However, the presence of irrigating solutions with varying electrical conductivity may influence their accuracy.

Aim

To evaluate and compare the clinical accuracy of the E-PEX Apex Locator and Propex Pixi Apex Locator in determining working length in the presence of different root canal irrigants.

Materials and Methods

This in vivo study was conducted on thirty single-rooted premolar teeth indicated for nonsurgical endodontic treatment. Actual working length was determined using a size #10 K-file under magnification and confirmed using digital calipers. Electronic working length measurements were obtained using the E-PEX Apex Locator and Propex Pixi Apex Locator in the presence of 0.9% saline, 2.5% sodium hypochlorite, and 17% EDTA. Measurements were repeated three times and averaged. Radiographic verification was performed using standardized intraoral periapical radiographs. Statistical analysis was carried out using one-way ANOVA and post hoc Bonferroni tests.

Results

The mean root canal length measured using radiographic and electronic methods showed no statistically significant difference for both apex locators ($p > 0.05$). The mean deviation from actual working length was 0.17 ± 0.33 mm for the E-PEX Apex Locator and 0.15 ± 0.23 mm for the Propex Pixi Apex Locator, indicating comparable accuracy between the devices. Irrigating solutions significantly influenced electronic measurements ($p = 0.001$). Saline demonstrated measurements closest to the control values, whereas sodium hypochlorite and EDTA showed comparatively greater deviations. However, all measurements remained within clinically acceptable limits.

Conclusion

Both the E-PEX Apex Locator and Propex Pixi Apex Locator demonstrated reliable and clinically acceptable accuracy in determining working length in the presence of various irrigating solutions. Although irrigants influenced electronic measurements, both apex locators can be safely used in routine endodontic practice for accurate working length determination.

Keywords: Electronic apex locator, working length, E-PEX, Propex Pixi, sodium hypochlorite, EDTA, saline, endodontics.

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Introduction

Successful endodontic treatment depends upon accurate cleaning, shaping, and obturation of the root canal system. Determination of the correct working length is one of the most critical steps in root canal therapy, as instrumentation beyond or short of the apical constriction may compromise treatment outcomes. Accurate working length determination has a profound effect on root canal preparation, microbial disinfection, and the hermetic seal of the root canal system. Correct canal length is also necessary to minimize the extrusion of infected debris into the periapical tissues. The outcome of treatment in teeth with necrotic pulps and periapical lesions is significantly influenced by the apical level of root canal filling.¹ Preparation of the canal, especially in the apical segment, without weakening the remaining dentin or perforating the root, is essential for proper disinfection. Therefore, virtually all stages of endodontic therapy require precise working length determination to ensure that neither the root canal system nor the periodontal ligament is damaged.² The apical constriction or minor diameter is considered the ideal endpoint for canal preparation and obturation because it represents the narrowest portion of the root canal and provides favorable healing conditions. However, anatomical variations in the cemento-dentinal junction (CDJ) and apical constriction make accurate determination of working length challenging.³

Traditionally, radiographic methods were used for working length determination; however, these methods possess limitations such as image distortion, anatomical superimposition, and radiation exposure. Furthermore, radiographs provide only a two-dimensional image of a three-dimensional structure and may not accurately identify the apical constriction. To overcome these shortcomings, electronic apex locators (EALs) were introduced and have become an integral part of modern endodontic practice because of their improved accuracy and reduced dependence on radiographs.⁴

The concept of electronic working length determination was first proposed by Custer, who suggested that root canal length could be estimated using electrical current. Later, Suzuki demonstrated that the electrical resistance between the periodontal ligament and oral mucosa remains constant at approximately 6.5 k Ω . Based on this principle, Sunada introduced the "biological characteristics theory" into clinical practice and reported that a constant resistance value of 6.2 k Ω exists between the oral mucosa and periodontium irrespective of age, sex, tooth type, or canal curvature.

The first-generation apex locators were based on resistance measurements using direct current; however, inaccuracies due to moisture and canal contents limited their effectiveness. This led to the development of second-generation apex locators based on single-frequency impedance measurements using alternating current. These devices also demonstrated limitations because the presence of conductive materials such as blood, tissue fluids, or irrigants within the canal could affect measurement accuracy.⁵

Modern third-generation apex locators utilize multiple-

frequency impedance principles and are capable of providing accurate readings even in the presence of electrolytes and irrigating solutions. These devices determine the position of the apical constriction by analyzing the ratio of impedances at different frequencies, thereby improving precision under varying canal conditions.⁶

The Propex Pixi Apex Locator developed by Dentsply Sirona is a compact third-generation apex locator that uses advanced multi-frequency technology to accurately determine working length in both wet and dry canals. The device does not require calibration or zero adjustment and provides both visual LED indicators and progressive audio signals to guide file progression toward the apex. Its compact pocket-sized design improves portability and operator convenience while reducing the need for repeated radiographs during treatment.⁷

Similarly, the E-PEX Apex Locator is a modern multi-frequency electronic apex locator designed to provide reliable and accurate working length determination under various canal conditions. The device incorporates automatic calibration, digital impedance analysis, and a large LCD display to improve precision and ease of operation. It is compact, rechargeable, and compatible with endodontic motors, offering additional functions such as apical reverse, apical slow down, torque reduction, and auto start-stop features that enhance clinical efficiency and safety.⁸

Root canal irrigants such as sodium hypochlorite, chlorhexidine gluconate, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), and saline are routinely used during biomechanical preparation because of their antimicrobial activity, tissue dissolution properties, lubrication, and smear layer removal ability. However, these irrigants differ in their electrical conductivity and may influence the accuracy of electronic apex locators. Sodium hypochlorite is highly conductive because of its ionic composition, whereas EDTA and saline exhibit different conductive characteristics.⁹ Since apex locators are frequently used in canals containing irrigants, evaluation of their performance in the presence of these solutions is clinically important.

Previous studies have demonstrated that modern apex locators maintain acceptable accuracy in the presence of irrigants. Jenkins et al. reported that electronic measurements obtained using modern apex locators remained accurate in the presence of sodium hypochlorite, EDTA, and other irrigating solutions.¹⁰ Similarly, Wrbas KT et al observed that contemporary multi-frequency apex locators provided reliable measurements under various canal conditions. However, slight variations in accuracy may occur depending on the conductivity of the irrigant and the design of the apex locator.¹¹

Therefore, the present in vivo study was undertaken to evaluate and compare the accuracy of two frequency-based electronic apex locators, namely the E-PEX Apex Locator and Propex Pixi Apex Locator, in determining working length in the presence of commonly used root canal irrigants including 0.9%

saline, 2.5% sodium hypochlorite, and 17% EDTA.

Materials And Methods

The present in vivo study was conducted in the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, India, after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee.

A total of thirty patients scheduled for nonsurgical endodontic treatment participated in the study. Thirty single-rooted premolar teeth with completely formed apices, confirmed radiographically, and indicated for endodontic treatment were selected. Standardized preoperative intraoral periapical radiographs were obtained for all teeth. Teeth exhibiting internal or external resorption, severe canal curvatures, open apices, canal obliteration, perforation, incomplete root formation, or radiographically invisible canals were excluded from the study. Pregnant women and patients with cardiac pacemakers were also excluded.

Informed written consent was obtained from all participants prior to treatment, and all procedures were explained to the patients. Local anesthesia was administered using 2% lignocaine with 1:200,000 adrenaline. Access cavity preparation was performed using high-speed round diamond burs, and the root canals were identified. Coronal preflaring was carried out using ProTaper SX hand files (Dentsply Maillefer, Switzerland), and pulp extirpation was performed using a barbed broach. Canal patency was confirmed by introducing a size #10 K-file (Mani Inc., Tochigi, Japan) passively through the apical foramen.

Determination of Actual Working Length

The actual length (AL) was determined by introducing a size #10 K-file into the canal until the file tip became just visible at the apical foramen under $\times 2.5$ magnification. The length was measured using a digital caliper. The actual working length was established by subtracting 0.5 mm from the measured length. These measurements were considered the gold standard and were compared with the electronic working length measurements obtained using the apex locators.

Electronic Working Length Determination

Working length was determined using the following electronic apex locators:

1. E-PEX Apex Locator (Eighteenth Medical, Changzhou Sifary Medical Technology Co. Ltd., China)
2. Propex Pixi Apex Locator (Dentsply Sirona, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland)

Initial electronic measurements were obtained before irrigation and considered as the control readings. Subsequently, canals were irrigated with distilled water using a 26-gauge irrigating syringe.

The following irrigants were used during the study:

- 0.9% Saline (Clarix Life Sciences Ltd., India)
- 2.5% Sodium hypochlorite (Vishal Dentocare, India)

- 17% EDTA liquid (Bombay Dental Surgicals Pvt. Ltd., India)

Prior to measurements, care was taken to ensure that the circuits, batteries, and operating modes of both apex locators were functioning properly. The canals were irrigated with the respective irrigant using a 26-gauge beveled needle attached to a 2 mL syringe. Excess irrigant was removed from the pulp chamber using cotton pellets and gentle air drying, while maintaining canal moisture.

A size #15 K-file (Mani Inc., Tochigi, Japan) attached to the file clip of the apex locator was introduced into the canal until the device indicated the "APEX" reading. The file was then withdrawn slightly until the display indicated the "0.5" mark. The silicone stop was adjusted to the coronal reference point, and the file was removed. The distance between the silicone stop and the file tip was measured using a digital caliper to the nearest 0.5 mm and recorded as the electronic length (EL). Stable readings maintained for at least 5 seconds were considered valid.

Electronic measurements were repeated three times for each tooth, and the mean value was calculated. Ten teeth were evaluated for each irrigant with both apex locators. To minimize bias, the order of irrigant testing and device usage was alternated. Between irrigants, canals were flushed with distilled water and dried with paper points before subsequent measurements were performed.

Radiographic Verification

Following electronic working length determination, radiographic verification was carried out using a size #15 K-file positioned at the electronically determined working length. A working length radiograph was then obtained using standardized intraoral periapical radiographic technique. Radiographs were evaluated under magnification, and the distance between the file tip and radiographic apex was measured and recorded as the radiographic working length (RWL).

All clinical procedures and measurements were performed by a single operator to eliminate inter-operator variability. The obtained data were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis.

Result

The mean root canal length measured using the radiographic method and apex locator for the E-pex group was 21.17 ± 2.36 mm and 21.00 ± 2.42 mm, respectively. Statistical analysis revealed no significant difference between the two methods ($p = 0.84$). Similarly, in the Propex group, the mean root canal length obtained by radiographic method was 21.78 ± 2.05 mm, while that measured by apex locator was 21.63 ± 2.09 mm, showing no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.89$). This indicates that both apex locators demonstrated measurements comparable to the radiographic method. (Table 1)

Group	Type of Measurement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T value	P value
E-pex	Radiograph	30	21.17	2.36	0.33	0.84
	Apexlocator	30	21.00	2.42		
Propex Preiapex	Radiograph	30	21.78	2.05	0.20	0.89
	Apexlocator	30	21.63	2.09		

Table 1: Comparison of Root canal length between Radiographic and Different Apex locator

The mean deviation (accuracy) for E-pex apex locator was 0.17 ± 0.33 mm, whereas for Propex apex locator it was 0.15 ± 0.23 mm. The difference between the two devices was not statistically significant ($p = 0.82$), suggesting that both apex locators have similar accuracy in determining working length. (Table 2)

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T value	P value
E-pex	30	0.17	0.33	0.22	0.82
Propex	30	0.150	0.23		

Table 2: Comparison of accuracy of Apex locators

The mean root canal length values recorded with E-pex apex locator were 21.00 ± 2.42 mm for Control group, 20.63 ± 2.47 mm for Saline, 20.13 ± 2.35 mm for Sodium hypochlorite and 20.05 ± 2.46 mm for EDTA. A statistically significant difference was observed among the groups ($F = 79.23$, $p = 0.001$). This needs to be further analyzed using post hoc test. (Table 3) It is also shown in Graph 1.

Sub Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F value	P value
Control	30	21.00	2.42	79.23	0.001*
Saline	30	20.63	2.47		
Sodium Hypochlorite	30	20.13	2.35		
EDTA	30	20.05	2.46		

One-way ANOVA test, *Significant

Table 3: comparison of Root canal length using E-pex apex locator in presence of different irrigating solutions

Graph 1: Root canal length using E-pex apex locator in presence of different irrigating solutions

Post hoc Bonferroni analysis revealed statistically significant differences between all pairs except between sodium hypochlorite and EDTA ($p = 0.804$). This indicates that irrigating solutions significantly influence the working length measurements obtained using E-pex apex locator. (Table 4)

Subgroups	Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.
Control vs saline	.367	.079	0.001*
Control vs Sodium Hypochlorite	.867	.096	0.001*
Control vs EDTA	.950	.073	0.001*
Saline vs Sodium Hypochlorite	.500	.054	0.001*
Saline vs EDTA	.583	.059	0.001*
Sodium Hypochlorite vs EDTA	.083	.054	0.804

Post hoc Bonferroni Test, *Significant, #Non-significant

Table 4: Multiple comparisons between the mean difference of Root canal length using E-pex apex locator in presence of different irrigating solutions

The mean Root Canal Length using Propex Apex Locator in Presence of Different Irrigating Solutions were 21.63 ± 2.10 mm for Control group, 21.10 ± 2.07 mm for Saline, 20.60 ± 2.05 mm for Sodium hypochlorite and 20.60 ± 2.05 mm for EDTA. A statistically significant difference was observed among the groups ($F = 1814.57$, $p = 0.001$). This needs to be further analyzed using post hoc test. (Table 5) It is also shown in Graph 2

Sub Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F value	P value
Control	30	21.63	2.10	1814.57	0.001*
Saline	30	21.10	2.07		
Sodium Hypochlorite	30	20.60	2.05		
EDTA	30	20.60	2.05		

One-way ANOVA test, *Significant

Table 5: comparison of Root canal length using Propex apex locator in presence of different irrigating solutions

Graph 2: Root canal length using Propex apex locator in presence of different irrigating solutions

Post hoc Bonferroni analysis revealed statistically significant differences between all pairs except between sodium hypochlorite and EDTA. This indicates that irrigating

solutions significantly influence the working length measurements obtained using pro pex apex locator. (Table 6)

Subgroups	Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.
Control vs saline	0.533	0.023	0.001*
Control vs Sodium Hypochlorite	1.033	0.023	0.001*
Control vs EDTA	1.033	0.023	0.001*
Saline vs Sodium Hypochlorite	.500	.000	0.001*
Saline vs EDTA	.500	.000	0.001*
Sodium Hypochlorite vs EDTA	.000	.000	-

Post hoc Bonferroni Test, *Significant, [#]Non-significant

Table 6: Multiple comparisons between the mean difference of Root canal length using Propex locator in presence of different irrigating solutions

Discussion

Accurate determination of working length is a fundamental prerequisite for successful endodontic treatment. Proper working length ensures complete cleaning and shaping of the root canal system while preventing over instrumentation or under preparation of the canal. Instrumentation beyond the apical constriction may result in extrusion of infected debris, postoperative pain, delayed healing, and damage to the periapical tissues, whereas instrumentation short of the apical limit may lead to inadequate debridement and persistence of microorganisms within the canal system. Therefore, precise working length determination plays a crucial role in achieving successful endodontic outcomes.¹²

The apical constriction or minor diameter is considered the ideal apical endpoint for root canal preparation and obturation because it represents the narrowest portion of the root canal and provides the most favorable healing conditions. However, the anatomical position of the cemento-dentinal junction (CDJ) and apical constriction varies considerably among teeth and may change with age due to continuous cementum deposition.¹³ Owing to these anatomical variations, accurate identification of the apical limit using conventional radiography alone becomes difficult.

Radiographic methods have traditionally been used for working length determination, but they possess several limitations, including image distortion, superimposition of surrounding anatomical structures, and inability to accurately represent three-dimensional root canal anatomy. In addition, repeated radiographic exposure increases radiation risk to both patient and operator. To overcome these shortcomings, electronic apex locators (EALs) were introduced and have become an integral part of contemporary endodontic practice.¹⁴

Modern apex locators operate on the principle of impedance measurement using multiple frequencies and are capable of providing accurate readings even in the presence of electrolytes and irrigating solutions. In the present study, the accuracy of the E-PEX Apex Locator and Propex Pixi Apex Locator was evaluated in the presence of commonly used root canal irrigants such as saline, sodium hypochlorite, and EDTA.

The results of the present study demonstrated that both apex locators produced measurements within the clinically acceptable range of ± 0.5 mm from the actual working length. This range is widely considered highly accurate and clinically acceptable in endodontic practice. The findings indicate that both the E-PEX Apex Locator and Propex Pixi Apex Locator can reliably determine working length in the presence of commonly used irrigating solutions.

Among the irrigants evaluated, saline demonstrated readings closest to the control measurements, whereas sodium hypochlorite and EDTA showed comparatively greater deviations in electronic working length determination. This may be attributed to differences in the electrical conductivity of the irrigating solutions. Sodium hypochlorite, being highly conductive because of its ionic composition, may alter impedance values and influence electronic measurements. EDTA also demonstrated similar deviations, possibly because of its chelating properties and electrolyte content. However, the deviations observed with both irrigants remained within clinically acceptable limits.¹⁵

The findings of the present study are consistent with those of Jenkins et al., who reported that modern apex locators can accurately determine working length irrespective of the irrigating solution present within the canal. Similarly, Kang and Kim evaluated multiple electronic apex locators under various canal conditions and concluded that modern multi-frequency apex locators maintain acceptable accuracy in the presence of sodium hypochlorite, saline, chlorhexidine, and EDTA.¹⁶ Sakkir et al. also demonstrated that electronic measurements obtained using modern apex locators closely corresponded to the actual working length, with the majority of readings remaining within ± 0.5 mm of the apical constriction.¹²

Several authors have reported that the electrical conductivity of irrigants may influence the accuracy of apex locators. Sodium hypochlorite possesses high electrical conductivity because of its ionic nature, whereas EDTA and saline exhibit comparatively lower conductivity. Despite these differences, modern third-generation apex locators are designed to compensate for variations in canal electrolytes through multi-frequency impedance ratio technology, thereby improving measurement reliability.

Another important factor affecting apex locator accuracy is canal diameter and file size. Ebrahim et al. reported that larger apical diameters may reduce the accuracy of electronic measurements when smaller files are used because of insufficient contact between the file and canal walls. In the present study, standardized instrumentation and file sizes were used to minimize these variables and improve consistency of measurements.

The use of irrigating solutions during biomechanical preparation is indispensable because of their antimicrobial action, tissue dissolution properties, lubrication, and smear layer removal ability. Sodium hypochlorite acts as an effective tissue solvent and antimicrobial agent, EDTA acts as a chelating agent facilitating smear layer removal, and saline serves

primarily as a flushing solution. Since these irrigants remain within the canal during instrumentation, evaluation of their influence on electronic working length determination is clinically relevant.¹⁷

The present study has certain limitations. The sample size was relatively small, and only single-rooted premolar teeth were included. In addition, only three irrigating solutions were evaluated. Further studies with larger sample sizes, different tooth groups, and additional irrigants are recommended to validate the findings under broader clinical conditions.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of the present in vivo study, both the E-PEX Apex Locator and Propex Pixi Apex Locator demonstrated clinically acceptable accuracy in determining working length in the presence of various irrigating solutions. No statistically significant difference was observed between the two apex locators regarding overall accuracy. However, irrigating solutions significantly influenced electronic measurements, with saline showing measurements closest to the control values, while sodium hypochlorite and EDTA demonstrated comparatively greater deviations. Nevertheless, all measurements remained within clinically acceptable limits. Both apex locators can therefore be safely and effectively used in routine endodontic practice for electronic working length determination.

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